

1 Experimental demonstration of dispersion- 2 diversity multicore fiber optical beamforming

3 **MARIO UREÑA,* SERGI GARCÍA, JOSE I. HERRANZ AND IVANA GASULLA**

4 *ITEAM Research Institute, Universitat Politècnica de València, Camino de Vera 46022*

5 *Valencia, Spain*

6 **maurgis@iteam.upv.es*

7 **Abstract:** Phased array antenna (PAA) beam-steering in high radiofrequency bands
8 will be key for upcoming 5G & Beyond wireless communications systems. As a
9 compact and efficient solution to provide tunable beam steering simultaneously to
10 parallel antenna distribution and connectivity, we experimentally demonstrate, for the
11 first time to our knowledge, tunable optical beamforming implemented on a dispersion-
12 diversity multicore optical fiber. The uniqueness of this fiber lies in the fact that each
13 one of its seven step-index trench-assisted cores has been tailored to provide the
14 required chromatic dispersion to enable tunable optical true-time delay line operation.
15 Continuous 1D beam-steering was demonstrated by measuring the radiating pattern
16 of an in-house fabricated 8-element PAA in an anechoic chamber at the
17 radiofrequency of 26 GHz, sweeping the beam-pointing angle from -43° up to 40° by
18 varying the operating optical wavelength from 1542.50 up to 1548.28 nm. Next-
19 generation fiber-wireless communications systems will benefit from the demonstrated
20 dispersion-diversity MCF optical beamforming in terms of flexibility, versatility,
21 capacity, and connectivity along with reduced size, weight, and power consumption.

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24 **2. Introduction**

25 Optical beamforming for phased array antennas (PAAs) will play an essential role in
26 next-generation fiber-wireless communications, especially in very crowded scenarios
27 that require fast and accurate radio beam steering. As its basic building block, the true
28 time delay line (TTDL) is the key optical component that holds high-performance
29 optical beamforming as it prevents undesired beam-squint effects, which can be
30 particularly detrimental in case of broadband signals, [1]. Different technologies have
31 been proposed for the implementation of optical TTDL beamforming, including fiber-
32 based architectures that comprise dispersive fibers [2,3], fiber Bragg gratings [4] or
33 parallel single-mode fibers [5], as well as photonic integrated solutions [6]. But despite
34 the intense research activity, there is still need for a compact and efficient fiber-based
35 solution to support antenna radio beam steering along with parallel distribution and
36 connectivity. These properties are of special interest in centralized radio access
37 networks for 5G and Beyond, since they call for multiple-element PAAs with reduced
38 size as they must operate at high radiofrequencies such as the 26-GHz band, [7].

39 Multicore fibers (MCFs) have become one of the leading technologies to overcome
40 the ever-increasing capacity and parallelization demands in fiber-optic communication
41 networks [8]. Beyond high-capacity digital communications, MCFs exhibit great
42 potential in other application scenarios such as radio-over-fiber distribution and MIMO
43 antenna connectivity on one hand, as well as optical and microwave signal processing
44 on the other. In this context, we have previously proposed the use of dispersion-
45 engineered heterogeneous MCFs for compact fiber-distributed signal processing, i.e.,

46 the simultaneous processing and distribution of microwave and optical signals [9]. This
47 approach is based on the custom design of MCFs to act as tunable sampled TTDLs
48 where every core provides at the output a different time-delayed version of the
49 incoming signal which, in addition, can be continuously tuned by varying the operating
50 optical wavelength. Such a MCF-based TTDL is particularly attractive for next-
51 generation wireless communications systems, such as Beyond 5G, as it brings further
52 flexibility, versatility, capacity and connectivity along with reduced size, weight, and
53 power consumption.

54 Up to date, the reported MCF-based optical beamforming networks exploit the MCF
55 for mere distribution while the actual TTDL is implemented externally. In [10], optical
56 beamforming for a 4-element antenna was demonstrated on a Si_3N_4 integrated
57 photonic circuit based on a series of optical ring resonators that actuated as the TTDL.
58 Then, this system was followed by a 150-m 4-core homogeneous MCF with the only
59 functionality of providing antenna connectivity. Limited beam-steering from 11.3° to 23°
60 was demonstrated in a 26-GHz radiofrequency (RF) signal. Optical beamforming for a
61 50-GHz 2-element antenna was demonstrated in [11] by resorting to two external
62 variable optical time delay lines, after which 2 cores of a 2-km 7-core homogeneous
63 MCF were used, again, only for delivery purposes. Following a different rationale, we
64 proposed in [12] to exploit a heterogeneous MCF to provide both tunable TTDL
65 operation for optical beamforming and short-reach distribution to the antenna. In that
66 work, we simulated the equivalent array factor that could be obtained at 10 GHz from
67 the measured RF phase difference after MCF propagation, but no real antenna
68 beamforming was demonstrated.

69 In this work, we report, for the first time to our knowledge, the experimental
70 demonstration of optical beamforming for PAAs implemented on a 5-km
71 heterogeneous MCF composed of 7 customized dispersion-engineered cores that
72 offer tunable TTDL operation. We successfully demonstrate radio beam-steering within
73 an 83° range in an in-house fabricated 8-element PAA at the RF frequency of 26 GHz
74 exploiting the dispersion diversity of the MCF.

75 **3. Multicore fiber true-time delay line**

76 We have developed a 7-core heterogeneous MCF that operates as a tunable sampled
77 true time delay line, [12, 13]. Each fiber core n was designed and fabricated with distinct
78 radial dimensions and core material composition to provide a particular group-delay
79 dependence with the optical wavelength, $\tau_n(\lambda)$. Figure 1 (a) shows a photograph of the
80 cross-section of the MCF, which was fabricated by the company YOFC. It is 5-km long
81 and consists of 7 different trench-assisted step-index cores placed in a hexagonal
82 disposition inside a $147.5\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ fiber cladding diameter, with an averaged $41\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ core
83 pitch. The measured worst-case crosstalk for the whole fan-in + MCF + fan-out
84 structure is below -30 dB. The insertion losses range from 4.6 to 7.7 dB, in which the
85 propagation losses measured by an Optical Time Domain Reflectometer at an optical
86 wavelength of 1550 nm are 0.46, 0.31, 0.31, 0.50, 0.19, 0.20, 0.17 dB/km, respectively,
87 for cores 1 to 7.

88 The uniqueness of this fiber lies in the capability of providing the range of chromatic
89 dispersions required for continuously tunable sampled TTDL operation in a single
90 optical fiber. If we exploit the spatial diversity, i.e., each core provides a TTDL sample,
91 at the output of the L -km MCF link we will get a basic differential group delay between
92 adjacent cores ($\Delta\tau = \tau_n - \tau_{n-1}$) that is provided by the differential chromatic dispersion
93 ($\Delta D = D_n - D_{n-1}$) following $\Delta\tau = \Delta D \Delta L$. Therefore, linearly incremental differential group
94 delays with the optical wavelength require as well linearly incremental chromatic
95 dispersions (i.e., group delay slopes).

96 Figure 1 (b) depicts the measured spectral differential group delays between core
 97 7 and the rest ($\tau_7 - \tau_n$), where we can appreciate, on one hand, how the differential
 98 group delay slopes increase linearly with the optical wavelength and, on the other
 99 hand, a similar increment from core to core. Actually, the average measured chromatic
 100 dispersions D_n at the anchor wavelength $\lambda = 1530$ nm follow that incremental trend
 101 with values of 13.85, 14.95, 16.35, 17.30, 18.25, 19.30 and 20.30 ps/(km·nm),
 102 respectively for cores 1 up to 7. Cores 3 to 7 provide differential chromatic dispersions
 103 ΔD nearly 1 ps/(km·nm), providing a constant basic differential group delay between
 104 adjacent samples for optical wavelengths ranging from 1530 up to 1560 nm. However,
 105 cores 1 and 2 seem to have been more affected by fabrication inaccuracies and
 106 therefore do not provide the required ΔD within a 10-% margin of tolerance. Figure 1
 107 (c) illustrates the measured spectral basic differential group delay $\Delta\tau$ for cores 3 to 7.
 108 Red-filled squares represent the mean measured differential group delays, error bars
 109 show their maximum deviation, and the black solid line represents the trend line for the
 110 mean values. We see that these 5 cores provide a linearly incremental basic differential
 111 group delay with the optical wavelength without significant deviation in a 30-nm optical
 112 wavelength range. Then, up to 5-sample TTDL operation can be implemented in the
 113 space-diversity domain by using cores 3 up to 7, while all 7 cores are applicable to
 114 operate in the wavelength diversity domain or to implement any other application that
 115 does not require space-diversity signal processing with a constant basic differential
 116 delay.

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 118 Fig. 1. (a) Photograph of the fabricated MCF cross-section, (b) Measured differential
 119 group delays with respect to core 7 ($\tau_7 - \tau_n$), and (c) Mean value of measured basic
 120 differential group delay ($\Delta\tau$) for cores 3 to 7 (red-filled squares), along with the maximum
 121 deviation (error bars), the trend line for the mean $\Delta\tau$ (black line) and its estimated
 122 maximum deviation area (green area).

123 4. Phased array antenna

124 An 8-element microstrip PAA with an element spacing of $d = 5.77$ mm ($0.5\lambda_0$ at 26
 125 GHz) was designed and fabricated. Because of the large electrical size of available
 126 RF connectors at this band, an extension of the input lines ending at a stepped
 127 substrate outline was conceived to accommodate the connectors. Microstrip lines were
 128 properly shaped to ensure identical time delays from each input to its corresponding
 129 radiating element. Figure 2 (a) shows a 3D representation of the radiation pattern at
 130 26 GHz over the PAA, simulated by CST Microwave Studio, when all inputs are fed
 131 with a uniform amplitude and phase. As expected, a directive radiation pattern along
 132 array axis is achieved, with a small ripple due to the finite dielectric.

133 The antenna was fabricated at our facilities using a milling machine on a substrate
 134 Rogers RT5880 with a height of 0.381 mm and relative permittivity of 2.2. Figure 2 (b)
 135 shows a picture of the fabricated antenna, which has been measured in the band of
 136 interest. Figure 2 (c) represents the active S-parameters as a function of the RF
 137 frequency measured with a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA). It can be observed that
 138 signal reflection keeps mostly below the accepted threshold of -10 dB within the
 139 measured band. Finally, far-field radiation patterns have been measured in an

140 anechoic chamber at 26 GHz. Figure 2 (d) compares the measured embedded
141 radiation pattern of one representative antenna element with the simulated one, where
142 the typical rippled response along the non-directive plane is observed, with a -6-dB
143 beamwidth of around 120°.

144
145 Fig. 2. Phased array antenna. (a) 3D representation of the radiation pattern, (b)
146 Photograph of the PAA with the RF connectors, (c) Measured active S-parameters as
147 a function of the radiofrequency and (d) Measured radiation pattern for a single antenna
148 element compared with the simulated one.

149 150 5. Optical beamforming experimental results

151 We apply the developed MCF-based TTDL to experimentally demonstrate optical
152 beamforming for the PAA at the RF frequency of 26 GHz. By using cores 3 up to 7, we
153 implement a 5-element beamforming network for the PAA whose beam-pointing angle
154 is tuned as we vary the basic differential delay $\Delta\tau$ by changing the laser optical
155 wavelength of operation, as Fig. 1 (c) shows.

156 Figure 3 represents the experimental setup used to measure the radiation pattern
157 of the PAA in an isolated environment. Here, the optical signal coming from a tunable
158 laser is modulated using a dual-drive external modulator (EOM) with the RF signal
159 generated by a VNA. This signal is then amplified using an erbium doped fiber amplifier
160 (EDFA) and launched into the corresponding cores of the 5-km MCF. Variable optical
161 attenuators (VOAs) are placed in each core path to ensure uniform power distribution.
162 The signal from each core is detected and amplified using independent photodiodes
163 and RF amplifiers. The PAA along with the required optical and electrical devices are
164 placed inside the anechoic chamber and onto an antenna positioner. The received
165 power is then measured by means of a receiver horn antenna and amplified by a low
166 noise amplifier (LNA) to obtain the radiation pattern with the help of the VNA.

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Fig. 3. Experimental setup of the optical beamforming network for the fabricated PAA along with the radiation pattern measurement infrastructure. EOM: Electro-Optic Modulator, EDFA: Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifier, VNA: Vectorial Network Analyzer, VOA: Variable Optical Attenuator, PD: Photodetector, PAA: Phased Array Antenna, LNA: Low-Noise Amplifier.

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Figure 4 shows the inside of the anechoic chamber, where we can appreciate in the left photograph the front side of the transmitter antenna and in the right photograph the receiver antenna. The separation between both antennas is 3 meters. The transmitter antenna is held in an antenna positioner that allows a 180-degree azimuth rotation for the proper measurement of the radiation pattern. The MCF spool is placed outside the anechoic chamber. As we can see in the left photograph, after the fan-out, each output fiber is connected to an independent photodetector and RF amplifier, which are placed on the antenna positioner, and feeds the corresponding PAA input by means of a 1-meter RF cable.

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Fig. 4. Photographs of the inside of the anechoic chamber with identification of both antennas along with main devices at the transmitter side.

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Beam steering in the optical beamforming network is achieved by sweeping the operation optical wavelength. Figure 5 (a) illustrates the evolution of the beam pointing angle as a function of the optical wavelength. Different optical wavelength bands can be chosen to produce a beam steering of 180° in the typical EDFA optical wavelength range (i.e., 1530 – 1560 nm). As the single element radiation pattern of Fig. 2 (d)

190 shows, for absolute angles greater than 45° , the received power drops considerably,
 191 what limits the maximum beamforming angle we can achieve. Thus, we choose the
 192 optical wavelength band ranging from 1542.50 up to 1548.28 nm, which produces the
 193 desired range of beam pointing angles.

194 We then measured the radiation pattern at different optical wavelengths ranging
 195 from 1542.50 to 1548.28 nm in steps of 0.96 nm. This translates into time delays
 196 provided by the TTDL going from 62.5 to 91.36 ps in steps of 4.81 ps approximately.
 197 Figure 5 (b) depicts the measured radiation pattern for the 7 different optical
 198 wavelengths. The resulting beam pointing angle varies approximately from -43° up to
 199 40° . Minor discrepancies on the basic differential delay between cores affect the
 200 radiation pattern, causing main lobe broadening at angles farther from broadside
 201 direction and shifting the beam pointing angle slightly. The radiation pattern of the
 202 antenna elements also takes part here as it has substantial power variations, affecting
 203 the main lobe shape. In addition, slight mismatches between the theoretical and
 204 experimental beam pointing direction for angles farther than broadside can also be
 205 attributed to the antenna itself due to the higher attenuation for those angles, as the
 206 single element radiation pattern shows (black dashed line in Fig. 5 (b)).

207 We must note that high levels of intercore crosstalk could contribute to the main
 208 lobe broadening and reduce the main-to-side-lobe ratio. However, in our case,
 209 crosstalk among the five cores exploited for optical beamforming remains below -40
 210 dB, resulting in no significant effect on the radiation pattern.

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212 Fig. 5. (a) Simulation of the beam-pointing angle (in degrees) as a function of the optical
 213 wavelength. Filled circles indicate the chosen wavelengths for the experiment. (b)
 214 Measured radiation patterns of the whole PAA at different wavelengths (colored solid
 215 lines) together with that of a single radiating element of the PAA (black dashed line).

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217 6. Discussion

218 The performance of the implemented optical beamforming network could be affected
 219 by static sources of degradation, such as fiber bending and twisting, as well as by
 220 dynamic environmental fluctuations caused mainly by temperature deviations. Since
 221 once the MCF link is deployed in a given scenario, one should not expect significant
 222 fiber bending and twisting (which can be compensated once the system is set up), we
 223 will focus on possible temperature fluctuations. In [13], we experimentally evaluated
 224 the influence of temperature on the differential group delay between cores in a
 225 temperature-controlled chamber, observing a maximum skew below $1 \text{ ps}/^\circ\text{C}$. From that
 226 measurement, we draw in Fig. 6 the effect on the RF phase shift difference between
 227 adjacent cores at 26 GHz from 15°C to 35°C , where the maximum difference remains
 228 below 60° (i.e., less than $6^\circ/^\circ\text{C}$). Such a worst-case value would translate to an antenna

229 beam misalignment of $2^\circ/\text{C}$, which corresponds to a hypothetical situation where the
 230 phase difference between every pair of cores is given by the maximum value of $6^\circ/\text{C}$.
 231 As we can see from the different curves in Fig. 6, such a scenario is very unlikely.

232 All in all, our radio beam-steering experiment was carried in a controlled
 233 environment (anechoic chamber) where the temperature variation was kept below 1° .
 234 In that case, the beam misalignment remains below 1° . Depending on the application
 235 scenario, if considerable temperature fluctuations are expected, then some type of
 236 dynamic optimization of the differential time delay should be implemented after
 237 propagation through the MCF.

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239 Fig. 6. Temperature dependence of the RF phase shift difference between adjacent
 240 cores.

241 Beyond the 1D-beamforming experiment successfully demonstrated in this paper,
 242 dispersion-diversity MCF TTDs have the potential to enable reconfigurable 2D-
 243 beamforming by exploiting not only the dispersion-diversity dimension provided by the
 244 MCF, but also the wavelength-diversity dimension if we inject a set of equally-spaced
 245 optical wavelengths. While dispersion diversity allows for azimuth beam-steering by
 246 using the wavelength dependence of the core differential delays ($\Delta\tau = \Delta D\lambda L$),
 247 wavelength diversity will introduce elevation beam-steering by exploiting each core
 248 dependence of the differential delay between adjacent wavelengths ($\Delta\tau = D_n\delta\lambda L$ in
 249 core n , where $\delta\lambda$ is the separation between adjacent wavelengths). We must note that
 250 the addition of wavelength diversity will increase complexity and cost, as compared to
 251 the solely use of space diversity, because a multicarrier optical source, a wavelength
 252 multiplexer, and a series of wavelength demultiplexers will be needed, (similarly to
 253 other dispersive-fiber-based approaches exploiting wavelength diversity, as for
 254 instance [3] and [4]).

255 6. Conclusions

256 We have experimentally demonstrated, for the first time to our knowledge,
 257 continuously tunable optical beamforming for phased array antennas built upon a
 258 custom dispersion-engineered heterogeneous multicore fiber. The 5-km fiber
 259 comprises 7 different trench-assisted cores, where the refractive index profile of each
 260 core was individually addressed to fulfil the requirements for tunable sampled TTDL
 261 operation while providing low intercore crosstalk. Continuous beam-steering was
 262 demonstrated by measuring the radiating pattern of an in-house 8-element phased
 263 array antenna in an anechoic chamber at the RF frequency of 26 GHz, sweeping the
 264 beam-pointing angle from -43° up to 40° by varying the operating optical wavelength
 265 from 1542.50 up to 1548.28 nm.

266 All in all, dispersion-diversity MCFs open the door towards the implementation of
267 compact and versatile fiber-distributed signal processing, where both distribution and
268 processing functionalities are provided within the same fiber medium. Other RF and
269 optical signal processing functionalities, such as tunable microwave signal filtering,
270 arbitrary waveform generation as well as time differentiators or integrators, can also
271 be implemented by this approach.
272

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279

280 Disclosures

281 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

282 Data availability

283 Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this
284 time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

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